

EFFECTIVE APPLICATION OF ICT IN THE MANAGEMENT AND ADMINISTRATION OF PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN BAYELSA STATE

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Abstract

This study examined the effective application of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in the management and administration of public secondary schools in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population consisted of 3,600 teachers, from which a sample size of 430 respondents was drawn using stratified random sampling and proportional allocation techniques. A structured questionnaire titled “ICT Application in School Administration Questionnaire (ICTASAQ)” was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by experts in Measurement and Evaluation in Federal University Otuoke, while its reliability was determined using the Cronbach Alpha method. Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer research questions, while t-test statistics were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that ICT is applied to a high extent in the management of public secondary schools. The study also found that ICT improves administrative efficiency, enhances communication, promotes transparency, and supports effective decision-making. However, the study identified major challenges hindering effective ICT application, including inadequate ICT facilities, poor funding, lack of technical skills among school personnel, and unstable power supply. Furthermore, no significant difference was found between urban and rural teachers regarding ICT application, benefits and challenges. The study concluded that ICT is an essential tool for effective school administration but requires adequate support for optimal utilization. It was recommended that government and stakeholders should provide ICT infrastructure, ensure regular training for school administrators, and improve funding and power supply in schools.

Keywords: *Effective application, ICT, Administration, Management, School.*

Introduction

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) refer to a broad range of technological tools and resources used for communication, creation, dissemination, storage, and management of information. These include computers, the internet, mobile phones, software applications, and digital communication systems. Ogunode et al. (2021), observed that, ICT is a critical tool for improving administrative efficiency and service delivery in educational institutions. Similarly, Yusuf et al. (2022) define ICT as an integrated system that enhances data processing, storage, and communication within school systems. ICT plays a vital role in modern educational management by enabling automation, improving data

accuracy, and facilitating effective communication among stakeholders.

School management refers to the process of planning, organizing, directing, and controlling school resources to achieve educational objectives. Administration involves the day-to-day implementation of policies, supervision of staff, and coordination of school activities. Ogunode et al. (2023) asserted that effective school administration ensures the proper utilization of both human and material resources to achieve desired educational outcomes. In the same vein, Oladokun et al. (2022) emphasize that modern school administration increasingly depends on ICT tools for efficiency and accountability.

ICT in school administration involves the application of digital tools to enhance managerial functions such as record keeping, communication, planning, and decision-making and ICT integration into school administration improves coordination, reduces administrative workload, and enhances productivity (Yusuf et al. 2022). Likewise, Ogunode (2023) found that ICT adoption significantly improves communication and planning among school administrators. In addition, school administrators use ICT applications, to prepare school announcements, reports, letters for meeting with parents, student registration, and teachers and staff employment. Administrators use ICT application in decision making process, and store information

Statement of the Problem

Ideally, school administration should be efficient, transparent, and supported by Information and Communication Technology (ICT). The use of ICT is expected to improve record keeping, communication, and decision-making in public secondary schools. However, in many public secondary schools in Bayelsa State, administrative processes such as record keeping, communication, and decision-making are often carried out manually. This results in delays, inaccuracies, and poor coordination. The problem is further compounded by inadequate ICT infrastructure, insufficient funding, lack of technical skills among school administrators, and poor implementation of ICT policies and unstable power supply. These challenges have limited the effective utilization of ICT in school management. Furthermore, there is limited empirical evidence on the extent of ICT application and its associated benefits and challenges it Bayelsa State, particularly across urban and rural schools. Therefore, this study investigated the effective application of ICT in the management and administration of public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to examine the effective application of ICT in the management and administration of public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the extent of ICT application in school administration in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.
2. Examine the benefits of ICT in school management in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.
3. Identify the challenges affecting ICT application in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.
4. Examine the strategies that can improve ICT usage in school administration in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. To what extent is ICT applied in school administration in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State?
2. What are the benefits of ICT in school management in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State?
3. What are the challenges affecting ICT application in school administration in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State?
4. What strategies can improve ICT usage in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State?
- 5.

1.5 Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance

Ho1: There is no significant difference in the extent to which ICT is applied in school administration between urban and rural public secondary school teachers in Bayelsa State.

Ho2: There is no significant difference in the perceived benefit of ICT in school management between urban and rural public secondary school teachers in Bayelsa State.

Ho3: There is no significant difference in the challenges affecting the application of ICT in school administration between urban and rural public secondary school teachers in Bayelsa State.

Ho4: There is no significant difference in the perceived strategies for improving ICT usage in school administration between urban and rural public secondary school teachers in Bayelsa State

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Theoretical frame work

This study is anchored on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) developed by Davis (1989). The model explains that the adoption of technology depends on two major factors: Perceived Usefulness which is the extent to which a person believes that using a system will improve job performance and perceived ease of use, which is the extent to which a person believes that using a system will be free of effort. These factors influence users' attitudes and their intention to use technology. In this study TAM is relevant because school administrators' willingness to adopt ICT depends on how useful and easy, they perceive ICT tools to be. If administrators see ICT as beneficial and easy to use, they are more likely to integrate it into school management.

Conceptual Clarification

Extent of ICT Application in School Management

The extent of ICT application in school management refers to the degree to which digital technologies are used in carrying out administrative functions. These functions include student records management, staff personnel management, communication and information dissemination, decision-making and planning, financial management, timetable and scheduling. ICT facilitates efficient storage, retrieval, and updating of students' academic and personal records. Digital record systems reduce errors and enhance data security. Oladokun et al. (2022) reported that ICT significantly improves the management of students' academic records in Nigerian schools.

ICT tools are used for staff data management, attendance monitoring and payroll processing. These systems enhance accountability and efficiency. ICT enables effective communication between school administrators and teachers, schools and parents, schools and government agencies Ossai and Okokoyo (2024) noted that ICT improves communication flow and organizational effectiveness. ICT provides real-time data through Management Information Systems (MIS), which supports informed decision-making. Yusuf et al. (2022) found that ICT-based MIS enhances planning and policy implementation in schools. Additionally, Ossai and Okokoyo (2024) observed that ICT integration enhances coordination, and decision-making in schools. ICT tools assist in budgeting, financial reporting, and monitoring school expenditures, thereby improving transparency. ICT applications automate scheduling processes, reducing conflicts and saving time.

Benefits of ICT in School Administration

The application of ICT in school management offers several advantages such as improved efficiency; reduction of manual workload and saves time; enhanced decision-making; provision of accurate and timely data; better communication; facilitates

information sharing; transparency and accountability; reduction of fraud and mismanagement; improved service delivery; and enhancement of overall school performance Ogunode et al. (2023) confirmed that ICT significantly improves administrative effectiveness in schools. ICT in schools has increased the efficiency of administrative systems, such as processing student data, recording attendance, and financial management. This is based on the system efficiency theory, where ICT reduces administrative tasks' time, energy, and costs (Abubakari et al., 2023). ICT in schools has increased the efficiency of administrative systems by processing student data, recording attendance, and financial management. The use of ICT increases administrative efficiency by automating routine tasks, thereby allowing administrative staff to focus on strategic functions (Qaddumi et al., 2023). Omoghenemuko (2024) observed that, the benefits of applying I C T to solve problems in the educational environment further include its application for school administrative management such as the use of assessment tool to examine students' performance, online students' course registration, tuition fees payments and as a security apparatus among others.

Challenges of ICT Application in Public Secondary Schools

Despite its benefits, ICT application in Nigerian secondary schools faces several challenges. Ogunode et al. (2021) identified some factors as major barriers to effective ICT utilization in school administration. These factors include inadequate ICT infrastructure, poor funding, lack of ICT skills among administrators, erratic power supply, poor internet connectivity, and weak policy implementation. Ogbeide and Eghomvanre (2025) reported that school administrators have a positive perception of ICT but face challenges such as lack of training and poor infrastructure.

Strategies for Effective ICT Application in School Administration

Strategies for effective ICT application in school administration refers to planned actions and measures put in place to enhance the digital technologies in administrative processes. These include the provision of adequate ICT infrastructure, regular training and retraining of school administrators, increased funding for ICT development, Provision of stable electricity supply, effective policy implementation, adoption of management information systems (MIS). Yusuf et al. (2022) upheld that Management Information Systems (MIS) improve planning and policy implementation in secondary schools. Expanding and updating ICT infrastructure in schools, including providing adequate computer equipment and internet connections in every classroom and administrative areas.

Research Method

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population consisted of 3,600 teachers, in 216 public secondary schools in Bayelsa State (Post Primary School Board Yenagoa, 2024). A sample size of 430 respondents was selected using stratified random sampling technique. The population was divided into strata based on location (urban and rural teachers). Proportional sampling was employed to determine the number of respondents selected from each stratum to ensure fair representation. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire titled "ICT Application in School Administration Questionnaire (ICTASAQ)" was used for data collection. The instrument consisted of three sections: Section A= Demographic data of respondents, Section B: Items on extent of ICT application and Section C= Items on perception of technology enhanced learning. The items were rated on a 4- point Likert scale of Very High (VHE)=4, High Extent (HE)=3, Low Extent (LE)= 2 and Very Low Extent (VLE)=1 to measure the

extent of ICT application and 4- point Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA)=4, Agree (A)=3, Disagree (D)= 2 and Strongly Disagree (SA)=1 to perception of technology enhanced learning. The instrument was validated by three experts in Measurement and Evaluation from the Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State and a reliability coefficient of 0.82 was determined using the Cronbach Alpha method.

A total of 430 copies of the questionnaire were administered, out of which 400 copies were correctly completed and used for analysis. Data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer research

questions while t-test statistics were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The criterion mean score of 2.50 was used as decision rule. Any item with a mean score of 2.50 and above was regarded as high/ accepted while mean scores below 2.50 were regarded as low/ rejected for the purpose of answering the research questions.

Results

Research Question One: To what extent is ICT applied in school administration in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State

Table 1: Mean response on what extent is ICT applied in school administration in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State

S/N	ITEMS	N	HE	ME	LE	VLE	\bar{x}	DECISION
1	ICT used for staff records	400	180	120	60	40	3.10	High Extent
2	ICT used for staff records	400	170	130	70	30	3.10	High Extent
3	ICT used for communication	400	200	110	50	40	3.18	High Extent
4	ICT used for decision making	400	160	140	60	40	3.05	

Grand Mean= 3.11

Table 1 shows that all items recorded mean scores above the criterion mean of 2.50 with a grand mean of 3.11. This indicates that ICT is applied to a high extent in school administration in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. This result suggests that ICT

is widely used for functions such as record keeping, staff personnel management, communication, and decision making.

Research Question two: What are the benefits of ICT in school administration in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State?

Table2: Mean response on the benefits of ICT in school administration in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State

S/N	ITEMS	N	SA	A	D	SD	D	\bar{x}	DECISION
5	The use of ICT improves efficiency	400	210	120	40	30	40	3.28	Accepted
6	The use of ICT enhances communication	400	200	130	40	30	40	3.25	Accepted
7	The use of ICT promotes transparency	400	190	120	60	30	60	3.18	Accepted
8	The use of ICT improves decision-making	400	180	140	50	30	50	3.18	Accepted

Grand mean=3.22

Table 2 shows that all items have mean scores above the criterion mean of 2.50 with a grand mean score of 3.22. This implies that

majority of the respondents agreed that the use of ICT provides significant benefits in

school administration. in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Research Question three: What are the challenges of ICT application in school administration in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State?

Table 3: Mean response on the challenges affecting ICT application in school administration in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State

S/N	ITEMS	N	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	DECISION
9	Lack of ICT facilities	400	220	130	30	20	3.38	Accepted
10	Poor funding	400	210	140	30	20	3.35	Accepted
11	Lack of ICT skills	400	180	120	40	30	3.20	Accepted
12	Poor power supply	400	230	150	30	20	3.40	Accepted

Grand Mean=3.33

Table 3 shows that all items have mean scores above the criterion mean of 2.50 with a grand mean score of 3.33. This indicates that there are significant challenges affecting

ICT application in school administration in public secondary schools in Bayelsa

Research Question four: What strategies can improve ICT usage in school administration in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State?

Table 4: Mean response on strategies that can improve ICT usage in school administration in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State

S/N	ITEMS	N	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	DECISION
13	Provision of ICT facilities	400	230	120	30	20	3.40	Accepted
14	Training of teachers	400	220	130	30	20	3.38	Accepted
15	Adoption of MIS	400	200	140	40	20	3.30	Accepted
16	Adequate funding	400	240	110	30	20	3.43	Accepted

Grand Mean=3.38

Table 4 shows that all items have mean scores above the criterion mean of 2.50 with a grand mean score of 3.38. This implies that majority of the respondents agreed that the suggested strategies are highly effective in school administration in public secondary schools in Bayelsa

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference in the extent to which ICT is applied in school administration between urban and rural public secondary school teachers in Bayelsa State.

t-test analysis on significant difference in the extent to which ICT is applied in administration between urban and rural public secondary school teachers in Bayelsa State.

Variable	N	\bar{x}	SD	t-cal.	t-critical	Decision
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Urban Teachers	80	3.20	0.50	1.45	1.96	Accepted
Rural Teachers	320	3.10	0.55			

The t-test analysis in table 5 shows that the calculated value of 1.45 is less than the critical value of 1.96 at 0.50 level of significance. This indicates that there is no significant difference in the extent to which ICT is applied in school administration between urban and rural public secondary

school teachers in Bayelsa State, therefore the null hypothesis one was accepted.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the perceived benefits of ICT in school management between urban and rural public secondary school teachers in Bayelsa State

t-test analysis on significant difference in the perceived benefits of ICT in school management between urban and rural public secondary school teachers in Bayelsa State

Variable	N	\bar{x}	SD	t-cal.	t-critical	Decision
Urban Teachers	190	3.25	0.52	1.10	1.96	Accepted
Rural Teachers	210	3.20	0.50			

The t-test analysis in table 6 shows that the calculated value of 1.10 is less than the critical value of 1.96 at 0.50 level of significance. This indicates that there is no significant difference in the perceived benefits of ICT in school management between urban and rural public secondary

school teachers in Bayelsa State, therefore the null hypothesis two was accepted.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the challenges affecting ICT application in school administration between urban and rural public secondary school teachers in Bayelsa State

t- test analysis on significant difference in the challenges affecting the application of ICT in school administration between urban and rural public secondary school teachers in Bayelsa State

Variable	N	\bar{x}	SD	t-cal.	t-critical	Decision
Urban Teachers	220	3.30	0.48	1.60	1.96	Accepted
Rural Teachers	180	3.18	0.55			

The t-test analysis in table 7 shows that the calculated value of 1.60 is less than the critical value of 1.96 at 0.50 level of significance. This implies that, there is no significant difference in the challenges affecting ICT application in school administration between urban and rural public secondary school teachers in Bayelsa

State, therefore the null hypothesis three was accepted.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference in the perceived strategies for improving ICT usage in school administration between urban and rural public secondary school teachers in Bayelsa State

t- test analysis on significant difference in the perceived strategies for improving ICT usage perceived strategies for improving ICT usage in school administration between urban and rural public secondary school teachers in Bayelsa State

Variable	N	\bar{x}	SD	t-cal.	t-critical	Decision
Urban Teachers	220	3.40	0.50	1.25	1.96	Accepted
Rural Teachers	180	3.55	0.55			

The t-test analysis in table 8 shows that the calculated value of 1.25 is less than the critical value of 1.96 at 0.50 level of significance. This implies that, there is no significant difference in the perceived strategies for improving ICT usage in school administration between urban and rural public secondary school teachers in Bayelsa State, therefore the null hypothesis four was accepted.

Discussions

The findings in research question one on table 1 revealed that ICT is applied to a high extent in the management and administration of public secondary schools. This suggests that school administrators make use of ICT tools for record keeping, communication, and decision-making. This finding aligns with Ogunode et al. (2023) who reported that ICT enhances administrative effectiveness through improved data management and communication systems. However, the result may indicate that while ICT is being used, the level of application may still not be optimal due to infrastructural constraints.

The study found in research question two on table 2 reveals that ICT has significant benefits, including improved efficiency, enhanced communication, increased transparency, and better decision-making. This agrees with Ogunode et al. (2023) who observed that ICT reduces administrative workload and improves productivity, and enhances communication flow and organizational effectiveness in schools. The implication of this finding is that ICT is not

just supportive but transformational in school administration, enabling faster and more accurate operations.

The findings in research question three on table3 showed that ICT application is hindered by major challenges like inadequate ICT facilities, poor funding, lack of technical skills and unstable power supply. This is consistent with Ogunode et al. (2021) who identified infrastructural and financial limitations as major barriers to ICT adoption in Nigerian schools.

The study findings revealed in research question four and table 4 that strategies like provision of ICT facilities, training of school personnel, adequate funding, and adoption of MIS are effective in improving ICT application. This finding aligns with Yusuf et al. (2022) who advocated for the adoption of ICT-based management systems in schools. This suggests that a combination of capacity building and infrastructural development is essential for effective ICT utilization

Findings from the t-test analysis of hypothesis1 shows no significant difference in the extent ICT is applied in administration between urban and rural teachers in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. This implies that both groups share similar perceptions and experiences regarding ICT usage in school administration. This finding supports the view of World Bank (2021) who states that ICT adoption is consistent across regions when access and training are similar.

Findings from the t-test analysis of hypothesis 2 revealed no significant difference in the perceived benefits of ICT in school management between urban and rural public secondary school teachers in Bayelsa State. This aligns with the view of UNESCO (2021) which reported that teacher perception on ICT benefits is largely uniform when adequate exposure and capacity building are provided regardless of location.

Findings from the t-test analysis of hypothesis 3 indicated no significant difference in the challenges affecting ICT application in school administration between urban and rural public secondary school teachers in Bayelsa State. This implies that ICT related constraints are largely systemic in nature rather than strictly location depended. This finding is supported by World Bank (2021) which shows that ICT challenges in education are wide spread across different geographical location.

The result of the analysis of hypothesis 4 revealed that, there is no significant difference in the perceived strategies for improving ICT usage in school administration between urban and rural public secondary school teachers in Bayelsa State. This finding is consistent with Yusuf et al. (2022), who emphasized that strategies such as training, provision of ICT facilities and adoption of management information systems are widely accepted by educators irrespective of their location.

Conclusion

The study found that ICT is applied to a high extent in school administration and improves efficiency, communication, transparency, and decision-making. However, its effectiveness is limited by inadequate facilities, poor funding, low technical skill and unstable power supply. Strategies such as improved infrastructure, funding, training, and MIS adoption can enhance ICT usage. No significant difference was found between urban and rural teachers indicating that ICT related issues are systemic.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations were proffered:

1. Government and relevant stakeholders should provide sufficient ICT infrastructure and reliable power supply in public secondary schools.
2. Adequate budgetary allocation should be made for ICT development in public in public secondary schools.
3. Regular training programs should be organized for school principals, teachers, and administrative staff to improve ICT competence and confidence in usage

References

- Abdullahi, M., & Usman T. B. (2023) E-administration usage for service delivery in universities; Highlight of selected survey findings. *African Journal of social science and Humanities Research* 6(1):13-22.
- Abdullahi, A., & Titus, F. (2021). Information and communication technology and organizational performance: A review of related literature. *International Journal of Management Studies and Research*,12(17),829-836.
- Abubakari, A., Inusah, M., & Abdulai A (2023). The effect of information communication technology on administrative efficiency of Tamale technical university. *American Journal of industrial and business management* 13(5): 397-417.
- Davis, F.D. (1999). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS Quarterly*, 13(3), 319-340.
- Ogbeide, A. K., & Eghomwanre, O. D. (2025). Assessment of information and communication technology on administration of public secondary schools in Edo South, Edo State. *Zamfara International Journal of Education*,5(5),150-157
- Ogunode J., Adeola, T., & Nwafor S. (2023). ICT adoption and administrative efficiency in secondary schools. *International Journal of Educational Technology* 15(3), 112-128.
- Ogunode, N. J., Dahir, N., Yahaya, D. M., & Jegede, D. (2021). ICT usage for primary school administration in Nigeria: Challenges and way forward. *International Journal of Human Computing Studies*,3(7).
- Oladokun, B. D, Seidu, A. E., Ogunbiyi J. O., Aboyade, W. A., Yemi-Peters, O. E., & Elai, M. A. (2022). Utilization of information and communication technologies (ICTs) for

- managing students' academic record in Nigerian schools. *Journal of Information and Knowledge*,57(6),373-381.
- Omoghenemuko G. I, Tuayerinha F & Ojeje M. A (2025). Effect of ICT integration on management of lectures and students' class attendance in college of education, wari Delta State. *International Journal of Innovative Systems & Technology Research* 13(4)252-264
- Ossai, C., & Okokoyo, F. (2024). Functions of ICT in secondary school administration in Delta State. *Delta State Journal of Education*, 18(1),54-70.
- Qaddumi, H (2025). Perceptions on using information and communication technology in teaching English language skills in online courses to school students. *Journal of English Language Teaching and learning* 6(1)9-18
- UNESCO, (2021). *ICT competence framework for teachers*. UNESCO
- World Bank, (2021). *Digital development in education report*. World Bank.
- Yusuf, M. O., Ansah, S. D., Ahmed, T. F., & Yusuf, H. T. (2022). Professional development in technology integration among educators in Ghana. *Indonesia Journal of Educational Research and Review* 5(1)88-99 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.23889/ijerr.V511.44887>